

Year of enactment of national legislation relevant to the control of invasive alien species for countries signatory to the Convention on Biological Diversity (as of October 2009)

Country	Year	Country	Year
Afghanistan	2005	Denmark	1992
Albania	2006	Djibouti	
Algeria		Dominica	
Angola		Dominican Republic	2000
Antigua and Barbuda		Ecuador	
Argentina	1997	Egypt	1983
Armenia	2002	El Salvador	1994
Australia	1999	Equatorial Guinea	
Austria		Eritrea	2006
Azerbaijan		Estonia	2001
Bahamas		Ethiopia	2008
Bahrain		Fiji	
Bangladesh	1973	Finland	1996
Barbados		France	2007
Belarus		Gabon	
Belgium	1973	Gambia	1977
Belize	1984	Georgia	1996
Benin	1991	Germany	2002
Bhutan	1995	Ghana	
Bolivia		Greece	
Bosnia and Herzegovina		Grenada	1986
Botswana		Guatemala	1999
Brazil	1967	Guinea	1990
Brunei	2007	Guinea-Bissau	
Bulgaria	2002	Guyana	
Burkina Faso	1994	Haiti	1986
Burundi	2000	Honduras	
Cambodia		Hungary	1996
Cameroon		Iceland	1999
Canada	1992	India	
Cape Verde	2002	Indonesia	
Central African Republic		Iran	
Chad	1998	Iraq	
Chile		Ireland	1976
China		Israel	1974
Colombia	1999	Italy	2003
Comores	1994	Jamaica	
Congo		Japan	2004
Cook Islands		Jordan	2003
Costa Rica	1997	Kazakhstan	1994
Cote d'Ivoire		Kenya	
Croatia	1994	Kiribati	
Cuba	1993	Korea, Republic of	1997
Cyprus		Kuwait	
Czech Republic	1992	Kyrgyzstan	
Democratic People's Republic of Korea		Lao	
Democratic Republic of the Congo		Latvia	2005

Country	Year	Country	Year
Lebanon		Rwanda	2005
Lesotho		Saint Kitts and Nevis	
Liberia	2002	Saint Lucia	1980
Libyan Arab Jamahiriya		Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	1987
Liechtenstein		Samoa	2005
Lithuania	1997	San Marino	
Luxembourg	2004	Sao Tome and Principe	
Macedonia	2004	Saudi Arabia	
Madagascar		Senegal	
Malawi	1992	Serbia	
Malaysia		Seychelles	1996
Maldives		Sierra Leone	1972
Mali	1995	Singapore	1994
Malta	2001	Slovakia	1994
Marshall Islands	1975	Slovenia	1999
Mauritania		Solomon Islands	1998
Mauritius	1993	South Africa	2004
Mexico	1988	Spain	1989
Micronesia (Federated States of)	1975	Sri Lanka	1999
Moldova	1998	Sudan	
Monaco		Suriname	
Mongolia		Swaziland	1981
Montenegro		Sweden	2004
Morocco		Switzerland	1981
Mozambique		Syrian Arab Republic	
Myanmar	1993	Tajikstan	
Namibia		Tanzania	2004
Nauru		Thailand	
Nepal		Timor-Leste	2003
Netherlands	1998	Togo	
New Zealand	1993	Tonga	
Nicaragua	1999	Trinidad and Tobago	2005
Niger	1998	Tunisia	1999
Nigeria		Turkey	
Niue		Turkmenistan	
Norway	1983	Tuvalu	1984
Oman		Uganda	1996
Pakistan		Ukraine	2001
Palau	1975	United Arab Emirates	2001
Panama	1995	United Kingdom	1981
Papua New Guinea		Uruguay	1997
Paraguay	1992	Uzbekistan	
Peru	2000	Vanuatu	2002
Philippines	2001	Venezuela	
Poland	2008	Viet Nam	
Portugal	1999	Yemen	
Qatar		Zambia	1991
Romania		Zimbabwe	2002
Russian Federation	1995		